

Supplementary Material for Research Paper

”Exploring Explainability: A Definition, a Model, and a Knowledge Catalogue”

Larissa Chazette*

*Leibniz University Hannover, Software Engineering Group, Hannover, Germany

[†]Leibniz University Hannover, Cluster of Excellence PhoenixD, Hannover, Germany

[‡]Saarland University, Institute of Philosophy and Department of Computer Science, Saarbrücken, Germany

Email: {larissa.chazette, wasja.brunotte}@inf.uni-hannover.de, timo.speith@uni-saarland.de

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I. ABOUT

This is the supplementary material for the research paper ”Exploring Explainability: A Definition, a Model, and a Knowledge Catalogue” accepted at the IEEE 29th Requirements Engineering Conference [1]. Since the space allocated for research papers did not suffice to elaborate on all research results, this document serves to amend this lack. In particular, more details on the Systematic Literature Review (SLR) – e.g., inclusion/exclusion criteria, complete list of analyzed papers, codes, etc. – and our workshops can be found here. For a deeper understanding of the supplementary material we recommend to have a look at the corresponding paper [1].

The specific content of this work is structured as follows. In the next section (Sec. II), our SLR is explained in more detail. Specific details will be given about how we selected the venues for our manual search and, more generally, about our inclusion and exclusion criteria and the selection procedure. Furthermore, all papers found during the SLR will be mentioned.

Sec. III will link the final selection of our papers with how they answer our research questions (RQs). We provide two tables, one for RQ1 and the second for RQ2 and RQ3.

In Section IV, we will present the codes resulting from our coding process for the data related to RQ2 and RQ3. We deliberately do not present codes from RQ1, as we have coded more categories and data than presented here or in the corresponding research paper. We will address these categories codes in a future publication. For the purposes here, TABLE II should be sufficient to illustrate our codes.

Finally, we will elaborate the workshops in detail in Sec. V. This includes all activities that the participants had to do before and during the workshops.

II. SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW

The search strategy for our interdisciplinary SLR consisted of a manual search and a snowballing procedure. During manual search, an investigator scans specific sources such as proceedings or journals issue by issues and paper by paper. To this end, we first identified relevant sources from different domains (e.g., computer science, philosophy). Subsequently, the selected sources were independently evaluated by researchers of the specific domains. The sources shown in TABLE I were part of the manual search. The *Total Retrieved* column indicates the total number of papers that were reviewed for eligibility in the respective source. *Initial Selection* contains the number of papers that had been pre-selected for closer review. The *Final Selection* column indicates the number of papers that met our inclusion criteria and thus belonged to the set of our final identified papers.

Since we conducted an interdisciplinary SLR, sources from other disciplines were also considered during the manual search. In addition to computer science, the disciplines of philosophy and psychology were chosen because they have decades of experience in the field of explanation research. Furthermore, during the snowballing process, other research areas are also taken into account. We believe that the choice of sources for our manual search is sufficiently representative to uncover research concerning explainability. Due to the fact that we also applied snowballing, further venues that are substantial for explainability were also covered.

TABLE I: Manual Search Sources and Paper Selection

Source	Total Retrieved	Initial Selection	Final Selection
International Requirements Engineering Conference (RE)	1312	15	4
Symposium on the Foundations of Software Engineering (FSE)	667	8	2
Information and Software Technology (IST) ¹	2668	23	0
Intelligent User Interfaces (IUI)	1158	52	18
Journal of Systems and Software (JSS) ²	4121	8	0
Transaction on Software Engineering (TSE)	2910	23	0
Conference on Information and Knowledge Management (CIKM)	2789	8	2
International Working Conference on Requirement Engineering: Foundation for Software Quality (REFSQ)	328	4	0
Transactions on Software Engineering and Methodology (TOSEM)	615	4	1
Conference on Recommender Systems (RecSys)	521	15	6
Requirements Engineering Journal (REJ)	455	9	2
RE Workshops	21	4	1
REFSQ Workshops ³	162	5	1
Minds and Machines	724	30	17
Big Data & Society	284	16	6
International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence - Workshop on eXplainable Artificial Intelligence ⁴	63	41	34
Philosophy and Technology ⁵	259	10	9
Ethics and Information Technology	538	1	1

A. Publication Selection

We included publications that met the following inclusion criteria (IC):

- IC_1 Address one or more of our research questions
- IC_2 Were published between 01/1984 and 03/2020
- IC_3 Are peer-reviewed journal, conference, and workshop publications

and we excluded publications that met the following exclusion criteria (EC):

- EC_1 Are non English-language publications
- EC_2 Are tutorials, proposals, and other non-peer reviewed publications

¹20 publications out of 2668 publications were not accessible.

²Seven publications out of 4121 publications were not accessible.

³Only the proceedings of the years 2000, 2001, 2006-2008, 2010, 2011 and 2015-2019 were accessible.

⁴Proceedings from 2017-2019 were considered

⁵Only the issues beginning from 2011 were accessible.

EC_3 Are publications exploring or proposing raw algorithmic techniques without further discussion about the theoretical background of explainability

We chose 1984 as the starting date because that was the year in which the first major work on explainability was published (namely, [2]). Furthermore, 03/2020 marks the time we started with the SLR. We are aware of the fact that 36 years is a long period of time. However, by choosing this time period, we wanted to get as broad an overview of the topic as possible. When it comes to explainability, it is important to recognize that this topic was already important in the eighties and is not as new a research field as often believed.

To include a publication, all inclusion criteria must be met. If at least one of the exclusion criteria was met, the publication was rejected. Formally expressed:

$$(IC_1 \wedge IC_2 \wedge IC_3) \wedge \neg(EC_1 \vee EC_2 \vee EC_3)$$

Fig. 1. Overview of our publication selection process

We manually reviewed all of the journals and conference proceedings by judging their relevance regarding our inclusion & exclusion criteria. We applied a two-phase selection procedure. In phase one, we have selected candidate papers based on title, abstract, and keywords. In cases where the

aforementioned elements did not provide sufficient information, we have also analyzed the conclusion section. EC_3 did not apply in this phase. In phase two, we have selected papers based on full text and also applied EC_3 . Fig. 1 illustrates this procedure. The procedure was the same for manual search and snowballing.

B. Found Papers

1) *Manual Search*: The following 104 papers are the result of our manual search and the application of our selection procedure: [3–106]

2) *Snowballing*: Since our review of the literature was partially based on the grounded theory approach to literature reviews proposed by [107], we stopped our snowballing process during the second snowballing iteration. Up to here, our data achieved a saturation and we have not gained any new insights nor have we discovered any new concepts or categories that arose from the data. The following 125 papers are the result of our forward & backward snowballing and the application of our selection procedure: [108–232]

III. REFERENCES FOR ANSWERING THE RQS

A. RQ1

We partially derived our presented definition related to RQ1 from the literature. As a first factor, the following sources highlight the importance of understanding: [5, 6, 12, 17, 21, 27, 30, 31, 33, 47, 52, 57, 70–73, 81, 88, 89, 92, 98, 99, 103, 105, 106, 108, 111, 113, 114, 116, 122, 123, 129, 132, 138, 139, 147–149, 152, 154, 157, 160, 164, 167, 168, 170–172, 175, 177, 180, 181, 187, 190–193, 197–199, 202, 203, 206, 208, 209, 212, 213, 221, 229, 232]. As a second factor, the following sources specified certain aspects of a system that should be explained:

TABLE II: Aspects to Explain (RQ1)

Aspect to explain	References
System in General	[27, 89, 91, 106, 137, 145, 149, 152, 162, 172, 187, 190, 212, 213, 221]
System's Reasoning Processes	[43, 72, 102, 147, 154, 167, 171, 172, 179, 218, 221, 222]
System's Inner Logic	[27, 30, 40, 57, 65, 90, 98, 103, 138, 147, 171, 225, 231]
System's Model's Internals	[10, 27, 70, 85, 98, 99, 127, 159, 160, 171, 175]
System's Intention	[111, 181, 221]
System's Behavior	[89, 91, 209, 218, 226]
System's Decision	[27, 79, 81, 118, 158, 159, 169, 190, 193]
System's Performance	[102, 197, 221]
Knowledge about User or World	[81, 89, 91, 193, 222]

B. RQ2 and RQ3

TABLE III: Quality Aspects Impacted by Explainability (RQ2 & RQ3)

Quality Aspect	References
Accountability	Pos: [6, 16, 53, 56, 59, 79, 115, 118, 132, 139, 141, 146, 159, 160, 166, 168, 171, 185, 189, 194, 211, 218, 230]
Accuracy	Pos: [36, 67, 104, 122, 176, 183, 225] Neg: [7, 14, 30, 56, 63, 93, 127, 135, 141, 146, 147, 151, 154, 190, 222]
Adaptability	Workshop Exclusive
Auditability	Pos: [21, 22, 27, 35, 39, 49, 58, 79, 82, 84, 85, 118, 122, 123, 167, 181, 183, 187, 190, 204, 206, 210, 214, 230]
Complexity	Workshop Exclusive
Compliance	Pos: [16, 54, 58, 95, 144, 147, 160, 211]
Confidence in the System	Pos: [17, 42, 43, 97, 110, 116, 117, 122, 127, 130, 136, 145, 148, 152, 155, 157, 162, 167, 168, 171, 177, 179, 185, 192, 198, 199, 210, 229] Neg: [41, 185, 214]
Correctness	Pos: [16, 118, 193]
Customer Loyalty	Pos: [17, 28, 50, 76, 101, 116, 137, 143, 182, 198]
Debugging	Pos: [11, 16, 30, 49, 55, 116, 122, 123, 136, 139, 141, 147, 148, 165, 168, 173, 187, 189, 190, 192, 211, 217, 228, 230, 231]
Decision Justification	Pos: [16, 30, 81, 110, 185, 190, 215, 222]
Development Cost	Neg: [30, 99, 106, 122, 135, 181, 190]
Effectiveness	Pos: [54, 95, 139]
Efficiency	Neg: [135, 141, 190]
Ethics	Pos: [6, 127, 147, 160, 181, 191, 229]
Extensibility	Workshop Exclusive
Fairness	Pos: [12, 22, 39, 57, 65, 68, 85, 118, 127, 139, 144, 146, 147, 152, 158, 162, 171, 185, 187, 189–191, 197]
Guidance	Pos: [9, 27, 40, 54, 118, 225]
Human-Machine Cooperation	Pos: [39, 59, 108, 152, 157, 187, 220, 232]
Knowledge Discovery	Pos: [9, 147, 152, 181, 187, 190, 191, 197, 211]
Learnability	Pos: [16, 75, 122, 148, 155, 157, 159, 166, 171, 172, 204, 212, 213, 230]
Maintenability	Workshop Exclusive
Mental Model Accuracy	Pos: [41, 63, 75, 84, 103, 123, 148, 162, 166, 167, 171, 178, 182, 197, 209, 214]
Model Optimization	Pos: [62, 139, 151, 152, 158, 187, 206, 211, 215]
Perceived Usefulness	Pos: [82, 83, 86, 112, 116, 131, 137, 161, 171, 172, 225]
Perceived Value	Pos: [80, 84, 95, 101, 116, 122, 143, 162, 171, 172, 179, 184, 190, 194, 195, 208, 209, 216, 225]
Performance	Pos: [94, 171, 197, 208, 232] Neg: [10, 27, 30, 32, 134, 135, 152]
Persuasiveness	Pos: [40, 50, 63, 76, 81, 82, 82, 99, 116, 117, 122, 131, 137, 143, 145, 153, 161, 166, 171, 185, 191, 195, 208, 210, 222, 225, 225, 230]
Portability	Workshop Exclusive
Predictability	Pos: [42, 63, 119]
Privacy	Pos: [78, 127, 160, 175, 187] Neg: [58, 78, 146, 152, 168, 189, 191, 192, 201]
Privacy Awareness	Pos: [152, 187, 216]

Real-Time Capability	Workshop Exclusive
Reliability	Pos: [160, 187, 223]
Robustness	Pos: [96, 151, 152]
Safety	Pos: [12, 115, 119, 127, 147, 187]
Scrutability	Pos: [54, 100, 116, 137, 139, 184, 185, 212, 222]
Security	Pos: [43, 127, 151] Neg: [15, 30, 43, 56, 58, 85, 120, 146, 189]
Stakeholder Trust	Pos: [5, 9, 12, 13, 15, 17, 22, 23, 28, 30, 32–34, 37, 39, 42, 43, 50, 52, 58–60, 63, 71, 72, 76, 78, 80–83, 85, 88, 91, 92, 94–100, 102, 104, 108, 110, 114–117, 119, 120, 122, 123, 126, 127, 132, 136, 137, 139, 142, 146, 147, 149, 151, 153–155, 157, 159, 160, 162, 166, 168, 172, 173, 179–182, 185, 187, 188, 190–193, 195, 205, 209, 216, 220, 222–225, 227, 229, 230, 232] Neg: [43, 63, 83, 85, 97, 99, 139, 179, 185, 192, 214, 225]
Support Decision Making	Pos: [9, 27, 40, 50, 81, 106, 112, 116, 122, 123, 131, 139, 152, 153, 161, 162, 171, 183, 191, 197, 210, 212, 225]
System Acceptance	Pos: [7, 9, 40, 42, 71, 78, 82, 91, 101, 119, 122, 123, 130, 137, 155, 162, 171, 172, 177, 181, 193, 195, 197, 198, 211, 224, 225]
Testability	Pos: [122, 147, 187]
Trade Secrets	Neg: [27, 56, 58, 146, 152]
Transferability	Pos: [152, 181, 186, 191]
Transparency	Pos: [9, 27, 33, 40, 43, 82, 88, 95, 101, 103, 110, 116, 122, 137, 139, 142, 148, 149, 155, 161, 167, 179, 181, 184, 185, 208, 220, 222, 224, 225]
Trustworthiness	Pos: [6, 7, 30, 51, 115, 117, 122, 148, 152, 159, 229, 232]
Understandability	Pos: [7, 13, 16–18, 27, 30, 36, 39, 46, 51, 54, 61, 74, 76–79, 83, 92, 95, 97, 102, 104, 109, 112–114, 116, 117, 123–126, 131, 132, 135, 139, 149, 151, 156, 157, 162, 166, 168, 171, 175, 176, 179, 190, 192, 198, 199, 208, 211, 214, 215, 220, 223, 232] Neg: [27, 99, 133]
Usability	Pos: [5, 27, 28, 30, 36, 50, 60, 92, 101, 116, 122, 135, 137, 161, 171, 178, 187, 192, 197, 216, 223, 225] Neg: [27, 41, 149]
User Awareness	Pos: [171, 178, 179, 192]
User Control	Pos: [6, 116, 147, 155, 191, 216]
User Effectiveness	Pos: [46, 81, 116, 117, 122, 145, 220, 222, 225] Neg: [66, 116, 214]
User Efficiency	Pos: [63, 83, 116, 122, 137, 145, 148, 185, 222, 225] Neg: [32, 83, 156]
User Experience	Pos: [50, 51, 80, 100, 182, 187, 192, 208] Neg: [27, 84, 166]
User Performance	Pos: [46, 122, 143, 162, 169, 172, 179]
User Satisfaction	Pos: [28, 40–42, 50, 60, 81, 83, 84, 99, 116, 122, 123, 135, 137, 142, 145, 153, 169, 171, 172, 177, 182, 184, 185, 188, 195, 198, 225]
Validation	Pos: [88, 112, 116, 122]
Verifiability	Pos: [42, 85, 97, 122, 158, 162, 167, 171, 173, 187, 199, 215]

IV. CODES - RQ2 & RQ3

In the material below, "P" indicates that explainability has a positive impact on the corresponding quality aspect, and "N" stands for a negative impact. We defined a threshold for producing a code during the coding procedure. This means

that only impacts were considered that were mentioned by at least *three* different sources. This approach was taken to ensure more reliable results. The material below is already cleaned up in this respect, such that codes that are not supported by at least three sources are not listed.

Accountability_P

- a critical piece in achieving accountability
- accountability
- allows to be held accountable
- assess accountability
- assignment of blame
- better manage liability
- enforce accountability under the law
- facilitate accountability
- fulfill the goal of accountability
- hold entities accountable
- important for responsibility of algorithms
- important for liability
- important to achieve responsible AI
- know where the blame lies when things go wrong
- legal accountability
- liability
- liability for machines
- means to promote accountability
- render decision-making more accountable
- render decisions more accountable
- shift responsibility from algorithm to participant
- used to determine legal culpability

Accuracy_N

- can negatively affect predictive accuracy
- cost of classification accuracy
- decrease in predictive performance
- inverse relationship between accuracy and explainability
- may conflict with precision
- requires a sacrifice for accuracy
- tension between accuracy and explainability
- the higher the accuracy, the lower the explainability
- the more explainable, the less accurate
- there is a well-known trade-off between accuracy and explainability
- trade off explainability against accuracy
- trade-off between accuracy and explanatory power
- yield lower accuracy

Accuracy_P

- improve classifiers
- improve prediction accuracy
- improve recommendation accuracy
- improved accuracy of decisions
- improving the accuracy
- improving the accuracy of VQA systems
- increase accuracy measures

Auditability_P

- allow the system to demonstrate partial capability
- allows for question-answering about the system's reasoning steps
- allows to look why the system has reached an anomalous result
- assess the reliability of systems
- auditability
- benefit the auditability
- describe the methods employed and the reasons for employing them
- detect errors in input data that led to adverse decisions
- enables models to be audited
- estimate likelihood of errors in decision making
- examine the knowledge of the system
- help to identify errors and biases
- help users understand what contributed to the large error
- identify that the system has erred
- indicate prior reliability
- is an auditable and provable way to defend algorithmic decisions
- judge whether a prediction is correct
- satisfying the desire to know whether an algorithm caused an error
- scrutinize individual cases
- support evaluation of system conclusions
- understand the scope of an error and solve discrepancies
- understand the underlying technicalities and models

Compliance_P

- ensure legal decisions are made
- implement a right to explanation
- make model performance and guideline compliance compatible
- necessary for compliance
- used to comply with regulatory and policy changes
- useful for increased compliance

Confidence in System_N

- decrease reliance if level of detail insufficient
- had a negative impact on user confidence
- question the system and lead to self-reliance

Confidence in System_P

- aim at acquiring confidence
- allow to develop appropriate reliance
- can lead to a higher level of confidence
- confidence
- confidence in decision making
- decides how much confidence to place in recommendation
- develop appropriate reliance
- higher confidence in system recommendations
- higher degrees of confidence
- improve confidence of the decision quality
- increase confidence in system's abilities
- increase reliance
- increase the end user's confidence in the system's conclusion
- increase user belief in system
- increase users' confidence in problem-solving competence
- increase user's confidence in the system
- increases their confidence
- instill confidence
- it can help build confidence
- might give us more confidence
- more user confidence
- significantly increase users' confidence
- strengthen the confidence of users

Correctness_P

- help correct errors in input data
- necessary for correcting an error
- optimality and correctness

Customer Loyalty_P

- affect perceptions of the organization
- could help inspire loyalty
- decrease the likelihood of abandoning the system
- higher degrees of rapport
- higher intention to use the interface again
- increase the probability of using the system
- it can help build rapport
- make users more willing to continue the use of a system
- promote rapport
- rapport

Debugging_P

- better debug the system
- debug predictive models
- debug the procedure
- debugging
- debugging purposes
- determine and fix errors and faults
- diagnosis and refinement
- ease of debugging
- enable users to debug the intelligent agent
- enables models to be debugged
- end-user debugging
- for debugging
- for system debugging
- help in locating sources of error
- help to identify and correct errors
- likely to be used for debugging

- model debugging
- notifying users about the defects in the system
- play an important role in debugging systems
- potential for aiding program analysis
- support developers for system debugging
- support system debugging
- used in system diagnosis

Decision Justification_P

- justification (e.g., offering reasons for an action).
- justification (of formal recommendations)
- justification (why recommendation was made)
- justify a given decision
- justify actions and decisions
- justify the decision made
- justify the outcome of a particular classification
- provides the required information to justify results

Development Cost_N

- at the expense of development effort
- can be costly on multiple dimensions
- cost expensive
- could be costly
- development cost
- development time
- is expensive

Effectiveness_P

- increase overall effectiveness
- system effectiveness limited by inability to explain
- useful for increasing an intelligent system's overall effectiveness

Efficiency_N

- could result in less efficient systems
- trade off explainability against efficiency

Ethics_P

- achieve an evaluation of the ethical standards of a machine
- achieve ethical AI
- ensure ethical decisions are made
- ethical decision making
- ethics
- evaluate if a decision is not in conflict with ethical norms
- promote ethics
- support ethical reasons

Fairness_P

- a way to check fairness
- address concerns about lack of fairness
- assurance that fairness issues have been mitigated
- demonstrate a model's fairness
- detect discrimination
- develop solutions against algorithmic discrimination
- enable people to identify and address fairness
- enable the identification of discrimination
- enables to assess whether algorithm is just
- ensure algorithmic fairness
- ensure fair decisions are made
- ensure fairness
- ensure that algorithms do not encode discrimination
- fair decision making
- fairness
- fulfill the goal of fairness
- identify algorithmic biases
- important to ensure algorithmic fairness
- inspect fairness
- mitigate decision biases
- moderate assessments of fairness
- non-discrimination
- render decisions more fair
- support fairness in decision-making
- verify fairness

- way to defend algorithmic decisions as being fair

Guidance_P

- educate about product knowledge
- guide in solving problems
- guide users during the use of the system
- increase product knowledge
- provide guidance on how to reverse adverse decisions
- to better guide the user
- to educate users about product knowledge

Human-Machine Cooperation_P

- allow for a better human AI cooperation
- crucial for effective human machine interaction
- improve cooperation
- improve the human-machine interaction performance
- key to effective human-AI interaction
- necessary for human in the loop
- provide a more effective interface for the human in-the-loop
- the ability of a model to be interactive with the user

Knowledge Discovery_P

- causality
- gain further insights or evidence
- helpful for knowledge discovery
- helpful tool to gain knowledge
- knowledge generation
- knowledge/scientific discovery

Learnability_P

- aid learning
- allow developers to not make the same mistake again
- allow users to learn something from the system
- allows the humans to learn
- can facilitate learning
- educate the user about the process of generating a recommendation
- facilitate learning
- help developers and humans working with a system learn from it
- help users to learn about how the system works
- improve user learning
- learn how the system operates
- learning how the system works
- teach something and learn
- teach users how to achieve a task

Mental Model Accuracy_P

- a tool to build and refine inner knowledge models
- align and adapt the mental models of the participating parties
- assist participants in the conception of an accurate mental model
- be aware of the system's limitations
- can help users to develop better mental models of systems
- create a shared understanding of decisions
- discover when a system is pushed over the bound of its expertise
- form accurate picture about the system's reliability
- gradually improve the mental model
- help build useful mental models
- help the user to build a theory of mind
- help users to understand when they can rely on the system
- helps users determine whether their needs are known by the system
- helps users to revise their theory of mind
- keep agents on the same page with respect to their beliefs
- know what the limitations of the system are
- learn the methods and knowledge used in the problem solving process
- users can judge whether their goal match those of the system

Model Optimization_P

- detect bias in training data
- detecting model bias
- determine what should be learned by a model
- identify bias in training data
- identify problems in training data
- improve and develop ML models

- lead to the design of better models

Perceived Usefulness_P

- assess whether a recommendations is useful
- crucial aspects for system utility
- effect on perceived usefulness of recommendations
- enhance perceived usefulness of advice
- increase perceived information usefulness
- increase the perceived usefulness of a recommender system
- perceived as a useful system
- perceived system usefulness
- usefulness

Perceived Value_P

- a sense of control for the user
- adds to business value
- affect perceptions of fairness
- be perceived as easy to use
- being perceived as a trustworthy system
- benefit perceived reliability
- better user perception
- convince users of of a system's competence
- help improve user perceptions during system errors
- help increase perceived benevolence
- increase perceived control
- increase perceived efficiency
- increase perceived fairness
- increase perceived recommendation quality
- increase perceived safety
- increase users' perception of system competence
- increases users' perception of the interface's competence
- influence the extent to which the decision is viewed as fair
- more positive perceptions of a system
- perceive as more helpful
- perceive the interface as more competent
- perceived to be fair
- perception of system ease-of-use
- positively affect perceptions of system effectiveness
- promote more positive user perception of the system
- raise perception of integrity
- result in more positive user perceptions
- system perceived as more competent
- useful for increasing perceived value

Performance_N

- drawbacks in terms of performance
- loading memory issue
- loading time issue
- may conflict with performance
- require high computational costs
- take time to compute
- trade-off at the expense of performance
- trade-off with the performance of a model
- use of CPU, memory, storage, and battery

Performance_P

- help to decide between models
- improve AI performance
- improve overall system performance
- increase system performance
- learning time can be reduced

Persuasiveness_P

- affect task-taking motivation
- convince the user that the agent is correct
- convince the user to accept the result
- convince users that the suggested alternative is appropriate
- convince users to adopt recommendation
- convince users to try or buy
- critical to acceptance of systems' decisions
- greater adherence to system recommendation
- help users to understand and accept a recommendation

- improve persuasiveness
- improve user acceptance of recommendations
- improve users' acceptance of recommendations
- increase acceptance of system conclusions
- increase persuasiveness of the recommended messages
- increase probability of accepting a suggestion
- increase the acceptance of recommendations
- increase the system's persuasiveness
- increased the acceptance of the recommendations
- increasing system persuasivness
- influence applicant reactions
- invoke user's interest in recommendation
- make recommendations more persuasive
- may accept the system's choices
- more compliance with a request
- motivate users to consume items
- nudge the user in a certain direction
- persuade users to make a certain choice
- persuade users to try or purchase a recommended item
- persuasion
- persuasiveness
- positively affect users' purchasing behgavior
- suggestions being accepted by users

Predictability_P

- ability to predict the system's performance correctly
- determine when the system will make a mistake
- increase the user's ability to predict the classifier decision
- makes users more likely to correctly predict the model's success

Privacy Awareness_P

- lower privacy concerns
- privacy awareness - ability to assess privacy
- provides a way to check privacy

Privacy_N

- can demolish stakeholder's anonymity
- can hurt privacy
- can threaten privacy
- could jeopardize privacy
- data privacy
- negative consequences regarding privacy
- pose a privacy risk
- privacy implications
- privacy issues regarding training data
- privacy might be violated

Privacy_P

- can help privacy
- ensure privacy is uphold
- ensure that sensitive information is protected
- privacy
- promote privacy

Reliability_P

- improve reliability
- reliability

Robustness_P

- facilitate robustness
- improve model robustness
- instrumental in developing more robust systems

Safety_P

- guarantee safety concerns
- guarantee safety concerns are met
- help create safer products
- help increase safety
- improve safety
- increase safety
- safety

Scrutability_P

- alter which features of an item are deemed most important
- customize recommendations to fit users' preferences
- explain corrections back to the system
- increase scrutability
- provide scrutability
- scrutability

Security_N

- allow for gaming
- can threaten security
- enable individuals to game the system
- enhance capabilities of attackers
- facilitate manipulations of the system
- introduce security vulnerabilities
- may conflict with security
- pose a security risk
- security implications
- trade off with security

Security_P

- bridge the gap between 'actual security' and 'perceived security'
- identify illegitimate intrusion, malware, and other attacks
- protection mechanism can be improved by public scrutiny
- security

Stakeholder Trust_N

- bad explanation-for-trust may fail to create trust
- bad explanations may lead to distrust
- can undermine trust
- decrease trust
- effects on trust
- erode trust
- may lead to mistrust
- may lose trust
- minimum explanations can potentially harm user trust
- too much explanation eroded user trust
- too much explanation can degrade trust

Stakeholder Trust_P

- achieve trust
- achieve user trust
- affect user trust
- agents tend to trust
- appropriately trust ML-based solutions
- assessing trust
- boost user trust
- breed trust
- build more trust in the interface
- build trust in the agent's choices
- build trust towards a machine's performance
- can address trust concerns
- can aim at acquiring trust
- can engender trust
- can promote trust in the system
- correctly calibrate trust in systems
- could help inspire user trust
- critical tool to build public trust in AI
- easier to trust
- enable domain experts and users to trust the model
- enable them to trust results
- enable to have appropriate level of trust
- engender trust in AI
- enhance trust in the classifier
- essential to assure trust
- foster trust
- foster user trust
- fundamental mechanism to increase user trust
- gain user trust
- generating trust in the model
- have a positive effect on user trust
- have the potential to build a trust relationship

- help gain user's trust
- help inspire trust in a recommender
- help promote trust
- help to establish a more appropriate level of trust
- impact perceptions of trust in the company
- important in assessing trust
- important in order to build human trust in systems
- improve user trust
- improving trust in decision by AI system
- improving trust in the advice
- increase trust
- increase trust in the recommender system
- increase trust in the system
- increases user trust
- increasing user trust
- instill trust
- means to establishing trust
- moderate trust to an appropriate level
- more likely to trust the underlying ML systems
- positive effects on organizational trust
- provide a way to check trust
- significant improvement in user trust
- significantly higher trust
- significantly increase users' trust
- students trust the system more
- support trust
- trust
- will enhance trust at the user side
- will trust the agent in the future

Support Decision Making_P

- aid the explainee in performing a task
- allow to make more accurate decisions
- allow to make more informed and accurate decisions
- allow users to make more informed decisions
- better decision whether to choose the recommended item
- employ for decision-making
- empower users to make informed choices
- enable users to make more accurate judgment on a decision
- enable users to make more informed and confident decisions
- enable users to make more informed decisions
- evaluate possible alternatives
- give enough information to decide
- help decide whether to engage with item further
- help facilitate improved user decisions
- help users make accurate decisions
- help users make to better decisions
- help users to evaluate items correctly
- help users to make more accurate decisions
- help users to resolve preference conflict
- helping users to make better decisions
- helping users to make good decisions
- improve the quality of user decisions
- improve users' decision making
- increased problem solving competence
- influence decision making
- make informed decisions
- might be critical to aid a person in making final decisions
- needed to make rational choices
- provide users with knowledge to make decisions
- support to make more accurate decisions
- support user decision-making

System Acceptance_P

- affect acceptance
- beneficial to the system's acceptance
- bring closer to acceptance by end users
- can enhance acceptability of systems
- can improve acceptance of recommender systems
- convince to use system
- determine the overall adoption
- essential for gaining acceptance

- gain user acceptance
- greater user acceptance
- higher degree of willingness to use systems
- higher level of willingness to use autonomous systems
- important for acceptance of recommender systems
- important for user acceptance
- increase acceptance
- increase user acceptance
- increasing user acceptance
- influential for acceptance of intelligent systems
- key towards acceptance of AI systems
- may increase system acceptance
- means of influencing user acceptance
- open the chance of adoption
- pivotal to acceptance by society
- potential to increase acceptance
- promote acceptance of the system
- requirement for model acceptance
- user acceptance

Testability_P

- enables models to be tested
- help system designers to evaluate or test a system
- helpful for testing

Trade Secrets_N

- cannot protect proprietary information
- disclose proprietary knowledge
- model confidentiality
- trade secret

Transferability_P

- improve transfer learning
- support transferability
- transferability

Transparency_P

- be perceived as transparent
- can provide transparency
- contribute to transparency
- could provide transparency
- foster transparency
- fulfill the goal of transparency
- improve transparency
- improve transparency of the system
- increase the system's transparency
- increase transparency
- increased transparency
- increasing perceived transparency
- increasing system transparency
- increasing transparency of system reasoning
- make more transparent
- offer transparency
- perceived to be transparent
- provide transparency
- provide transparency of how system works
- providing system transparency
- render decisions more transparent
- support transparency
- system transparency
- transparency

Trustworthiness_P

- achieve complete trustworthiness
- create more trustable products
- essential for becoming trustworthy
- foster trustworthiness
- important to achieve trustworthy AI
- improve untrustworthy models
- increase trustworthiness
- make it more trustworthy
- trustworthiness

- trustworthy AI

Understandability_N

- create false binaries
- hinder understanding if not appropriate
- may cause information overload

Understandability_P

- aid in understanding network mistakes
- aid in understanding an automated vehicle's function
- aid in understanding the decision's consequences
- allow its users to better understand its outputs
- allow to understand the behavior of a DNN
- allow users to understand why prediction is made
- assist understanding how the system processes data
- better understand what a model has learned
- can be easily comprehended
- can increase our understanding of the models
- can strongly influence users' understanding of complex data
- concerned with enabling human understanding
- effects on user understanding
- enable domain experts and users to understand the model
- enable human users to understand
- enable human users to understand AI systems
- enable understanding
- enhance understanding of training situations
- enrich people's understanding
- equip users to understand the system
- facilitate the understanding of the system
- get insights into predictions
- help a user to understand why an item is recommended
- help the human to understand the behavior
- help the human to understand why an agent failed
- help the user better to understand the rationale
- help user to understand agent behavior
- help user to understand why item is recommended
- help users to understand system's output
- help users understand the suggestions made
- help users understand the system's operation domain
- helpful for understanding intelligent system's reasoning process
- hint to better understanding of the job recommendations
- important for program comprehension
- important to understand how the system operates
- improve understandability of ML
- improve user understanding of the system
- improve users' understanding
- improving user understanding
- interpretability
- it can help build understanding
- key to understanding models better
- know the system's reasoning
- make decisions understandable
- make opaque algorithms more understandable
- positive effect on understandability
- provide insights into the model
- show a significant improvement in user understanding
- support intelligibility
- tell us something about the decision-making process
- tend to cause understanding
- tool to build understanding of the technology
- understand and contextualize the system strategy
- understand and evaluate the model
- understand system behavior
- understand system's reasoning
- understand the relevance feedback algorithm
- understanding
- understanding a system
- understanding how the application works
- understanding of why the outcome arose
- understanding system behavior
- way to better understand decisions
- way to interpret the decisions

Usability_N

- not every software should provide explanations
- reducing the sense of ease of use
- the focus is not on usability

Usability_P

- better utilize the AI
- can help reduce complex cognitive efforts
- crucial aspect for usability
- ease of use of the recommender system
- ensure effective interactions with ML systems
- help to improve the usability of the system
- improve usability
- increase ease of use
- leads to more effective use
- leads to more efficient use
- make better use of the system
- make effective use of system
- make it quicker and easier for users to find what they want
- reduce cognitive burden
- save user's cognitive effort
- save user's interaction efforts
- substantially affect usability
- to make a better use of a system's outputs
- usability

User Awareness_P

- can promote awareness
- increase situational awareness
- serve awareness

User Control_P

- control
- enable users to control their interaction more actively
- give greater control to the user
- human control over the decision
- meaningful human control over algorithms
- provide control
- starting point for better user control

User Effectiveness_N

- can be conflicting with effectiveness
- lead to agreement with incorrect system suggestions
- lead to automation bias when familiar with problem

User Effectiveness_P

- allow to assess whether the alternative is appropriate
- can lead to greater accuracy in decision making
- effectiveness
- improve users' decision effectiveness
- necessary for the user to carry out his or her task
- user effectiveness

User Efficiency_N

- require significant human effort
- taking more time
- users need to take time to analyze explanations

User Efficiency_P

- decreasing the time needed to reach a judgement
- help users make decisions faster
- help users make faster decisions
- reduce time for decision making
- user efficiency
- user's decision efficiency
- users need less time understanding the interface

User Experience_N

- become distracting over time
- can pollute user interface
- may have contributed to confusion or surprise
- too much explanation can create confusion

User Experience_P

- change user attitude towards the system
- improve users' experience
- influences actions, emotions and beliefs of the recipient
- lead to more positive user attitudes
- make the system more engaging
- play an important role in improving user experience
- promote feelings of familiarity
- user experience

User Performance_P

- affect test performance
- better user performance
- can increase performance on information retrieval tasks
- improve task performance
- improve user performance
- improved decision quality
- improved problem solving performance
- user performance

User Satisfaction_P

- be more comfortable
- brings enjoyment to users
- can increase user satisfaction
- can lead to higher level of satisfaction
- contributes to user satisfaction
- decrease frustration
- feel more comfortable
- has a positive effect on satisfaction
- higher degrees of satisfaction
- important for user satisfaction
- improved user satisfaction
- improving user satisfaction
- increase enjoyment
- increase satisfaction
- increase user satisfaction
- increase users' satisfaction
- increased participants' satisfaction with the recommendation
- lead to better user satisfaction
- lead to greater satisfaction
- lead to greater user satisfaction
- positive effect on satisfaction
- positive relationship with user satisfaction
- promote feelings of comfort
- satisfaction
- significantly impact satisfaction
- user satisfaction

Validation_P

- help users assess if the recommended alternative is truly adequate for them
- validate system knowledge
- way of validating the decision process of an AI
- way to verify the validity of a decision

Verifiability_P

- assess whether a prediction is accurate
- check the system by examining the way it reasons
- enable users to verify that an algorithm is accurate
- ensure that algorithms are performing as expected
- ensure that algorithms perform as expected
- evaluate correctness of system outputs
- evaluate the goodness of a match
- evaluate the proposed solution
- help users evaluate the accuracy of the system's prediction
- increase the ability to assess whether a prediction is accurate
- verification
- verify accuracy
- verify correct functioning
- verify that the system works as it should
- verify the correctness of the knowledge base or structure

V. WORKSHOPS

A. Workshop with Philosophers and Psychologists

The workshop with philosophers and psychologists consisted of one pre-workshop exercise and three workshop activities. The structure of the workshop is presented in Fig.2.

Fig. 2. Workshop with philosophers and psychologists

a) *Pre-workshop exercise:* We asked participants to prepare a definition of explainability according to the participant's background before our workshop. The idea was to collect these definitions before the discussion to allow for comparison and to avoid bias from our preliminary results and the debate.

b) *During the workshop:* In the first activity, we presented the categories regarding RQ1 found in the literature for discussion. We discussed whether these categories are accurate with what the participants consider explainability to be. In the second activity, the idea was to understand if the definitions found in the literature match participants' own definition of explainability, submitted before the workshop. We compared these categories and discussed the differences in order to reach a consensus. During the last activity, we discussed important *desiderata* for explainability. In this case, *desiderata* is the philosophical equivalent for quality aspects.

B. Workshop with Requirements Engineers

The workshop with requirements engineers consisted of one pre-workshop exercise and three workshop activities. The structure of the workshop is presented in Fig.3.

a) *Pre-workshop exercise:* For the preparation exercise, we asked participants to name quality aspects that are impacted by explainability. We sent a list of quality aspects resulting from our coding process without the detected polarities to avoid bias. To support participants, we also developed four hypothetical scenarios (Sec. V-C) where explainable systems had to be designed. The scenarios consisted of short stories describing a domain and a business problem related to the need for explainability. The goal was to help participants in better understanding contexts where explainable systems may

be needed. Based on the scenarios, we asked participants to specify desirable quality aspects for each system based on their expertise, and how explainability would interact with each of these aspects. Next, we asked participants to elaborate a list of the quality aspects and to specify if explainability would impact positively or negatively on each aspect. We also welcomed participants' suggestions about further quality aspects that could be connected to explainability but were not present in our list.

Fig. 3. Workshop with requirements engineers

b) *During the workshop:* In the first activity, we presented the list of quality aspect without polarities to the participants and asked them to set the polarities. We established a round structure for this activity, where each participant would first define the polarity, justify the decision and at the end of the round all participants could discuss each others' choices. The idea was to provoke debate and reach consensus. In the second activity, we compared the polarities given by the participants with the findings from our coding process. We compared the results and had an open discussion to discuss differences and reach consensus. Experts could relate to all polarities that they did not mention initially, but were found in the literature. In the third activity, we clustered the quality aspects collaboratively based on their relationship and discussed their impacts on the system.

C. Homework

For the workshop with requirements engineers, we designed the following hypothetical scenarios. Note that the workshops were originally in German, so the following scenario descriptions are translations.

a) *Loan Issuing Software:* Bank Tresor Holdings Ltd. wants to change its loan issuing software. In the past, the bank has often come under suspicion of including gender or ethnicity when determining creditworthiness. For this reason, the new system is to be equipped with a feature that will allow the employee to find out why a particular person gets the calculated credit score. The system should be able to explain to the employee what the most important factor was that contributed to that exact classification, and what the customer would have to change to get a different (better) credit score. Tresor Holdings employees are experts in their field and can work through even complicated issues in a way that customers can understand. The customers themselves do not get to see anything from the system.

b) *Medical Diagnosis System:* Saint Health hospital not only wants to help doctors make better judgments, but also to upgrade the doctor-patient interaction. To this end, it plans to introduce a new interactive disease prognosis system that not only reliably explains to doctors how a particular prognosis came about, but can also provide this information tailored to patients. With the help of the system, doctors will be able to better educate patients about their diagnoses so they can accept or reject a particular treatment in an informed and justified manner. Beyond being understandable to patients, of course, the system should also be able to provide doctors with additional specialist information that patients might not be able to relate to.

c) *Applicant Selection Software:* The company Good-Jobs wants to automate most of its hiring process. Before a select few applicants get a real interview, an initial screening is to take place completely online. The final result should not only be presented to the applicants, but also made comprehensible for them. Especially the rejected applicants should be able to understand what led to their rejection and how they can improve for the next time. The recipients of the explanations should not only be the applicants, but also the legal department, which must determine whether certain rejections were justified.

d) *Autonomous Driving:* The car manufacturer AutoNomous GmbH is the first car manufacturer in the world to offer fully autonomous vehicles. As with normal vehicles, however, accidents do occur from time to time with autonomous vehicles, but much less frequently than with conventional automobiles driven by humans. In order to be able to resolve these rare accidents without the help of experts, an explanatory component is to be added to the software. The company can no longer afford to provide an expert to analyze and assess each accident. The software extension should make it easy for accident investigators to find out for themselves what led to the accident and who is responsible.

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